

The Desirability of Westerners in India in Jhabvala's *A Backward Place*

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Abstract

Ruth Praver Jhabvala feels the burden of English men and women living in India. India is an overpowering and overwhelming entity that drives them onwards to the inevitable choice between drowning and disaster by staying on and escapes by withdrawal and flight. The Westerners are rich and prosperous. They are mobile, autonomous and self-dependent. Jhabvala's A Backward Place has westerners who happened to live in India. This paper attempts to expose what sort of hold and fall the westerners living in India have got. Jhabvala finds India, with its powerful impact of social and personal milieu, has forcibly brought about a conflicting status quo for them-either to stay on or to delight in the escapade of leaving the country.

Keywords: attraction, mobile, autonomous, self-dependent, culture, history, psychology etc.,

Ruth Praver Jhabvala expounds the burden of the English men and women living in India. For her view in India is an overpowering and overwhelming entity that drives them onwards to the inevitable choice between drowning and disaster by staying on and escape by withdrawal and flight of imaginations. The Westerners are rich and prosperous. They are mobile, autonomous and self-dependent. She consistently bases the conflicts that arise between Indians and westerners upon the complexities of culture, history, and psychology. Her novel *A Backward Place* has westerners who happened to live in India. Etta, Judy and Clarissa are poised at different points to undergo different emotional experiences. Their respective fates result as much from their being. Being a central European herself and being used to the affluent way of life in the west, Jhabvala personally considers India's poverty as the most salient feature of this country.

European women come to India impelled by different purposes. Some of them are drawn by the variety of the Indian life. Others come for the better knowledge of India's geography, art and culture. Still others come to India in search of peace of mind and soul. They are attracted by the Indian saints, whom they believe, have the power to unravel to them the mystery of life and to offer to them the light of truth. Jhabvala's main concern is with the quest of a woman for her identity and her validity as a human being. Usually, western women are portrayed as healthier as and happier than Indian women in her

novels. They enjoy greater social and cultural freedom. *A Backward Place* concerns itself with the narrator's refracting mirror splitting the image of her into a series of contradictory selves, deconstructing in unambiguous ways which appear as an integrated authorial personality. Shahane comments on the title of the novel as:

The most significant aspect of *A Backward Place* which strikes me as a major dement of Jhabvala's thought process is the dominant voice of affirmation which rings true and clear in the various chambers of its structure. Judy seems to me the central and main character in the novel who says "aye" to all the challenges that her life and experience present to her. More than Etta, more than Clarissa, Judy represents the authentic voice, the dominant note of this international orchestration in *A Backward Place*. (55)

It focuses on the cultural scene of Delhi in the 60's. An admirable study of an English girl, Judy who is married to an unsuccessful Indian artist named Bal. Jhabvala skillfully narrates her own complex response to India into the varied responses of her European characters while narrating her European characters in various types of cycle of response that she believes all westerners to go through in India.

The importance of main character of this novel is Judy. She comes to India after her marriage and never faces the problem of adjustment. Now, she wears a sari, grows her hair so long and lives with Bal's relatives without any problems. Singh describes: "Judy is far-sighted, soft-natured and understanding woman. She is mentally ready to compromise with life and help her husband to regain confidence and use his talent" (57). Etta and Clarissa are both foreigners and they play a crucial role in the novel. Etta, just like Judy, marries an Indian and comes to India at an early age. Residing in India for twenty Eve years, she marries three Indian boys one after the other. She dislikes India and points out India on many occasions. When we speak of Clarissa, another foreign lady, who comes to India on her own, is altogether so different. She is a good lady who develops the virtue of adjusting herself to what is given. She tells Sudhir: "Well, don't let's get too serious. Life is a jolly affair, so they tell me, and we have to take it with laughter, laughter all the way. Ugh" (153).

Jhabvala points out another category of foreigners through other three characters in this novel. These westerners come to India for a short life span on some specific condition. Here, we have the Hochstadts, an old German couple, living in Delhi. Dr. Hochstadts is an Economist and has come to India as a visiting Professor for a period of two years. Their attitude is quite different, mature and understandable. They maintain their western views and also appreciate the Indian art and Philosophy. They pontificate on the favourite theme of Jhabvala's East-West differences in the following words: "How often have I thought: ...' that a serious comparative study of Indian and 'western spiritual achievements will widen the horizons of both the one and the other" (106).

Jhabvala not only describes the western characters, but also a few Indian characters which appear to be quite insignificant when compared to western characters. Some of the Indian characters like Bal, Judy's husband is portrayed as a typical Indian youth. He is a graduate without any employment, but full of plans and builds castles in the air. Sudhir is Judy's colleague who belongs to Bengali family and his great-grandfather is a famous educationist and a leader of the Brahmo Samaj Movement. His grandfather is a distinguished Professor. But, unfortunately his father is an employee in a National Library. Sudhir is a brilliant student and studied History in the University. He searched for jobs in Calcutta, Delhi, Bombay, Poona, Patna and many other places but he does not find any. As the days passed, his father died leaving his mother and two daughters. After that, he got job in a very remote district of Orissa and worked in many organizations. He took the responsibility of his two sisters' marriage, one sister to an engineer in Jamshedpur and another sister to a doctor in Asanol. After his mother's death, he left Calcutta and shifted to Delhi. Sudhir

got job in a company “Cultural Dais”. His best friend Jayakar is an old retired man. Sudhir, Jayakar and Bal belong to the lower middle-class of Indian society. Singh quotes: “... the whole country is a “backward place”. Its poverty is appalling: But for the amelioration of the starving millions, Sudhir offers a solution, that is, he wants to run professional theatre to educate people through entertainment.” (58)

The other famous Indian woman character in this novel is Mrs.Kaul a modern sophisticated, cultured, educated, middle-aged woman. Mrs. Kaul, the Honorary Secretary of the “Cultural Dais” in Delhi appears to be a caricature of western woman, imitates western culture, but, neither remains an Indian nor a westerner. Connie Hayball describes her, “Out of all her characters, Mrs. Kaul, Secretary of the ‘Cultural Dais’ is snobbish and affected...” (59) The dishonest man is Kishan Kumar, super-actor, a friend of Bal appears to be a caricature of the Indian film stars. He maintains status in the society and promises young men like Bal. you will have an opportunity in the films. That is the reason all the youth meets him. There is another character named, Gupta or Guppy, a rich man and an owner of a big Hotel. A typical businessman is very rigid and traditional at home but feels free to do anything when he is in bazaar. Frequently, he goes out with Etta and has fun. On the other hand, Etta is also practical in leading her life even though she is married. She has a false assumption about marriages. She tells Judy: “Marriages, my dear, are made to be broken, that’s one of the rules of modern civilization. Just because we happen to have landed ourselves in this primitive society, that’s no reason why we should submit to their primitive morality” (5).

Etta describes India as a backward place. Judy submits everything to her Indian husband and seeks a new life in India with patience and hopes for the golden days in the future. Etta’s reaction is not normal. It is true that any foreign girl who marries an Indian, leaving her family and country forever, can at least hope to have a woeful living in India. She hates to see Judy living in this state and tells her. “You must leave him and get out. You’re just rotting here. Look at you in that thing’ ... and your hair too and ugh, you’re awful. You’ve let yourself go...” (6).

Clarissa is basically an artist and accepts every situation of life very happily. She is kind to the poor and humble towards people of India, leads a simple life. She comes to India in search of spiritual life and emerges from the library, holding aloft Rolland’s *Life of Vivekananda*, and says to Sudhir: “Do you know that it was this book that really and truly finally decided me to come to India? I’d wanted to come ever since I was a tot, but it was this-this dear, darling book’ --and she kissed it» ‘My Bible! My Guru!’” (115)

In this novel, Jhabvala describes the interior decoration of Etta’s apartment. Her apartment is so beautiful and elegant with no Indian aura; one can feel that you are living in Europe. When Judy visits Etta’s house she likes it: “The raw silk lampshades matched the curtains, and sophisticated black and white prints hung on the walls. There were two flowers each in two tiny delicate vases. Several gay record-sleeves were scattered on top of the radiogram; a French fashion magazine lay open on the divan” (6).

Etta asks Judy to look at herself in the mirror. Judy does not find anything strange and significant. But, Etta suddenly comes up behind her and pulls the pins out of her hair, which fall down her shoulders. With another tug, the sari drops off. “...There was Judy in her sari-petticoat and the short blouse, looking young and vigorous and pleasing, with her apple breasts, her bright blue eyes and her fair hair framing her face” (216) She stands blushing; her face too pale after ten years in India was suddenly the fresh pink it had been intended for. She still retains her charm. Then, Etta tempts her with an invitation to go with her to England, France, Italy or wherever she like and have to have a goodtime. But, Judy turns deaf ear to her tempting. Although embarrassed, “...she stooped to pick up her sari and tuck it back to her petticoat string” (217) Thus, Judy finds for herself a permanent place by identifying and submitting herself to the Indian ethos, which is odd for Etta and Clarissa.

They have crossed the cultural barriers but they are not always in it. But, Judy seeks identification with the Indian ethos and proves that she is a real Indian wife. Of course, there is a danger of retracting one's steps back to the world from which one came. Forster describes the humanist as possessing four leading characteristics "Curiosity, a free mind, belief in good taste, and belief in the human race." (64) "Curiosity" in *A Backward Place* obviously represents distinctive features of an alien ethos.

Thus, the analysis made hitherto in this paper attempts to expose what sort of hold and fall the westerners living in India have got. In *A Backward Place* there are three foreigners women. They are Clarissa and Judy from England and Etta from Hungary. Etta is single. Judy is wedded to Bal. Etta is divorced from three Indian husbands. Each woman has a totally different perspective on India. Jhabvala finds India, with its powerful impact of social and personal milieu, has forcibly brought about a conflicting status quo for them-either to stay on or to delight in the escapade of leaving the country. It is evident that these white are affluent and influential. Her characters Esmond, Etta, Judy and Clarissa, with their turbulent emotional bent and how they succeed in maintaining the psychological equilibrium and how they are aware that they were the cause of their destiny are the testimony of the attraction.

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